

ADVANCED FINITE ELEMENT VIBRATION ANALYSIS OF VARIABLE-THICKNESS VARIABLE-WIDTH LAMINATED COMPOSITE BEAMS

P. Salajegheh¹, R. Ganesan^{1*}

¹ Department of Mechanical and Industrial Engineering, Concordia University, Montreal, Canada,

* Corresponding author (ganesan@encs.concordia.ca),

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1 Introduction

Variable-width variable-thickness laminated composite beams provide stiffness-tailoring and mass-tailoring design capabilities. They are increasingly and widely being used in engineering applications including robotic manipulators, aircraft wings, space structures, helicopter blades and yokes, turbine blades, and civil infrastructure due to their enhanced stiffness-to-weight and strength-to-weight ratios.

These structures are subjected to time-varying loadings. In the present work, the free vibration of symmetric linear-thickness-and-width-tapered laminated composite beams is considered. In variable-thickness variable-width laminated composite beams, the stiffness and mass of the beam vary through its length.

There are plenty of works conducted on the free vibration of laminated composite beams, most of which are on the response of uniform-thickness uniform-width beams. Abarcar and Cunniff [1] conducted the free vibration analysis of uniform laminated composite beams using one-dimensional Kirchhoff laminated beam theory. Chandrashekhara et al. [2] have studied the free vibrations and obtained the natural frequencies of advanced composite beams. They have considered the effect of rotary inertia and shear deformation in the free vibration analysis of the beams. Vinson and Sierakowski [3] established an exact solution for the free vibration of simply-supported uniform laminated composite beams neglecting the effect of shear deformation. Krishnaswamy et al. [4] obtained analytical solutions to the free vibration of generally laminated composite beams including the effect of

transverse shear and rotary inertia in the energy formulation. Khdeir and Reddy [5] obtained analytical solutions for the free vibration of cross-ply rectangular beams with arbitrary boundary conditions. Reddy [6] and [7] studied the behavior of laminated composite beams and presented a finite element model to analyze the vibration of Euler-Bernoulli laminated composite beams. Berthelot [8] has worked on properties, free vibration and natural frequencies of laminated composite beams. Abramovich and Livshits [9] established analytical solution of free vibration and obtained the mode shapes and the natural frequencies of non-symmetrical cross-ply laminated beams. There also have been numerous researches on the free vibration of thickness-tapered beams. Roy and Ganesan [10] conducted a detailed study on the response of tapered composite beams having different types of thickness profile considering general boundary conditions. Farghaly and Gadelrab [11] have studied the free vibration of stepped uniform-width thickness-tapered Timoshenko composite beams using finite element method. He et al. [12] presented a complete review of different configurations of tapered composite structures. Zabihollah [13] and Eftakher [14] developed a conventional finite element model for thickness-tapered Euler-Bernoulli beams. Ganesan and Zabihollah [15] and [16] have presented a higher-order finite element formulation for thickness-tapered laminated composite beams based on classical laminated plate theory. To [17] have considered four degrees of freedom per node (deflection, rotation, curvature and gradient of curvature) and two nodes per element in the finite element formulations in order to obtain stiffness and mass matrices for linearly tapered beams based on Euler-Bernoulli beam theory. Badagi and Ganesan

[18] have studied the free vibration of thickness-tapered width-tapered laminated composite beams using Rayleigh-Ritz method. Salajegheh and Ganesan [19] have worked on the free vibration of variable-thickness variable-width laminated composite beams using conventional finite element formulation in which two nodes per element and two degrees of freedom per node were used.

In the present study the free vibration of variable-width variable-thickness laminated composite beams is considered. Simply-supported, clamped-clamped and clamped-free boundary conditions are considered for free vibration response. Comparison of the advanced finite element solution with the conventional finite element solution [19] is performed.

A comprehensive parametric study is conducted to investigate the effects of taper configurations, thickness-tapering angle, width-ratio (the ratio of the width of the beam at the right end to that of the beam at the left end) and boundary conditions on the free vibration of the composite beams.

2 Variable-width variable-thickness laminated composite beams

In general there are three types of thickness tapered beams: Externally-tapered, mid-plane-tapered and internally-tapered beams. Thickness tapering is achieved by terminating selected plies at specific locations through the length of the beam. Similarly, width tapering is done by linearly cutting the beam on the surfaces perpendicular to the mid-plane of the beam.

In this study, four types of internally-thickness-tapered configurations corresponding to four different types of plies drop-off, as shown in Figure 1, are considered.

The beam's width varies linearly along its length from b_1 at $x = 0$ to b_2 at $x = L$, as shown in Figure 2.

3 Advanced finite element analysis

3.1 Formulation

Considering a variety of tapered configurations according to different types of plies drop-off an advanced finite element formulation is developed based on the one-dimensional Kirchhoff laminated beam theory. Natural frequencies and mode shapes of different types of internally-tapered composite beams are determined.

In tapered beams the properties of the beam vary through the length of the beam. The equation of motion based on classical laminated beam theory [8] for a variable-width variable-thickness beam is:

$$\frac{\partial^2(b(x)\tilde{M}_x)}{\partial x^2} + b(x)\tilde{N}_x^i \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + q(x) = b(x)\rho_s \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} \quad (1)$$

in which $b(x)$ denotes the width of the beam. For a linearly width-tapered beam:

$$b(x) = b_l - \frac{(b_l - b_r)}{l}x \quad (2)$$

\tilde{M}_x denotes the bending moment per unit width about the y-axis, \tilde{N}_x^i is the axial force per unit width along the x-axis, w is the deflection in the thickness direction, $q(x)$ is the distributed transverse load per unit length, t represents time and ρ_s is mass per unit length per unit width expressed as:

$$\rho_s = \sum_{k=1}^n \rho_k (h'_k - h'_{k-1}) \quad (3)$$

Here n denotes the number of plies and ρ_k is the density of each ply. h'_k and h'_{k-1} denote distances to the top and to the bottom interfaces of each ply from the centerline of the beam respectively as shown in Figure 3.

In the present study width-tapering is described by the width ratio (r_b) as:

$$r_b = \frac{b_r}{b_l} \quad (4)$$

One can write the bending moment for thickness-tapered beams as [15]:

$$M_x = B_{11}(x)\varepsilon_x^0 \cos^4(\varphi) + D_{11}(x)\cos^4(\varphi)k_x \quad (5)$$

where $B_{11}(x)$ denotes the first coefficient of the coupling stiffness matrix, ε_x^0 is the strain in x -direction of the reference point, φ is the thickness-tapering angle, $D_{11}(x)$ is the first coefficient of the bending stiffness matrix and k_x is the curvature.

$$k_x = -\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \quad (6)$$

The first coefficient of the bending stiffness matrix is a function of x and varies through the length of the beam. For each element this coefficient is determined as [15]:

$$D_{11}(x) = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{3} (h_k^3 - h_{k-1}^3) \bar{Q}_{11k} \quad (7)$$

in which n is the number of plies in each element, \bar{Q}_{11k} is the first coefficient of the transformed reduced stiffness matrix of the ply k .

Since the considered beams are mid-plane symmetric, $B_{11}(x)$ will be equal to zero. The bending moment for symmetric thickness-tapered beams will be:

$$M_x = -D_{11}(x) \cos^4(\varphi) \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \quad (8)$$

Two nodes per element and four degrees of freedom (deflection, rotation, curvature and the gradient of curvature) per node are considered. A seventh-order polynomial is used for the expression of deflection to satisfy the boundary conditions.

Interpolation functions determined using advanced finite element formulations are given as:

$$N_1^e = 1 - \frac{35x^4}{l^4} + \frac{84x^5}{l^5} - \frac{70x^6}{l^6} + \frac{20x^7}{l^7} \quad (9a)$$

$$N_2^e = -x + \frac{20x^4}{l^3} - \frac{45x^5}{l^4} + \frac{36x^6}{l^5} - \frac{10x^7}{l^6} \quad (9b)$$

$$N_3^e = \frac{x^3}{6} - \frac{2x^4}{3l} + \frac{x^5}{l^2} - \frac{2x^6}{3l^3} + \frac{x^7}{6l^4} \quad (9c)$$

$$N_4^e = -\frac{x^2}{2} + \frac{5x^4}{l^2} - \frac{10x^5}{l^3} + \frac{15x^6}{2l^4} - \frac{2x^7}{l^5} \quad (9d)$$

$$N_5^e = \frac{35x^4}{l^4} - \frac{84x^5}{l^5} + \frac{70x^6}{l^6} - \frac{20x^7}{l^7} \quad (9e)$$

$$N_6^e = \frac{15x^4}{l^3} - \frac{39x^5}{l^4} + \frac{34x^6}{l^5} - \frac{10x^7}{l^6} \quad (9f)$$

$$N_7^e = -\frac{x^4}{6l} + \frac{x^5}{2l^2} - \frac{x^6}{2l^3} + \frac{x^7}{6l^4} \quad (9g)$$

$$N_8^e = -\frac{5x^4}{2l^2} + \frac{7x^5}{l^3} - \frac{13x^6}{2l^4} + \frac{2x^7}{l^5} \quad (9h)$$

Integrating the equation of motion by parts, the coefficients of stiffness and mass matrices for the beam are obtained respectively as [20]:

$$k_{ij}^e = \int_0^l b(x) D_{11}(x) \cos^4(\varphi) \frac{d^2 N_i}{dx^2} \frac{d^2 N_j}{dx^2} dx \quad (10)$$

$$m_{ij}^e = \int_0^l b(x) \rho_s N_i N_j dx \quad (11)$$

N_i and N_j represent the shape functions of the beam. Inserting the interpolation functions into equations (10) and (11), the coefficients of the stiffness and mass matrices for a thickness-tapered width-tapered element can be determined.

Equations (10) and (11) define two 8×8 matrices for each element which can be used to build the global stiffness matrix $[K]$ and global mass matrix $[M]$. Having the global stiffness and mass matrices for a beam, the natural frequencies and mode shapes can be determined by solving the eigenvalue problem:

$$([K] - \omega^2 [M])\{q\} = 0 \quad (12)$$

in which ω represents the natural frequency and $\{q\}$ represents the vector of the mode shape corresponding to each natural frequency. Having the above equations and performing the calculations using MATLAB[®] software, the natural frequencies and mode shapes of each beam can be determined.

3.2 Natural frequencies

The material considered in the analysis is pre-impregnated NCT-301 graphite-epoxy material supplied by NEWPORT Company, USA [21] with following mechanical properties. E_1 is 113.9 GPa, E_2 is 7.9856 GPa, ν_{12} is 0.288, ν_{21} is 0.0178, G_{12} is 3.138 GPa and density is 1480 kg/m³ [15]. Obtained results have been compared and validated for three cases:

I. Uniform-thickness uniform-width laminated composite beams: Accuracy of the natural frequencies obtained using advanced finite element formulation is compared with the accuracy of the existing results obtained using conventional finite element method [20]. The conventional finite element formulation considered for this case uses two nodes per element and two degrees of freedom (deflection and rotation) per node to analyze the vibration of the beams.

Uniform beams with a) simply supported, b) clamped-free and c) clamped-clamped boundary conditions are considered. Beams are made of 36 plies of NCT-301 graphite-epoxy prepreg and have 25 cm length and 2 cm width. The laminate configuration is $[0/90]_9$. The first three natural frequencies of the beams are considered. Accuracy of the results obtained using advanced finite element method compared to the results obtained using conventional finite element method is shown in Table 1.

In Table 1, NF denotes Natural Frequency and E represents the number of elements used, CFEM and AFEM represent Conventional and Advanced Finite Element Methods respectively. As it can be observed from Table 1, when applying the conventional finite element method and using only one element for the analysis, only the first and second natural frequencies of the simply supported and clamped-free beams and none of the natural frequencies of the clamped-clamped beam can be derived. Whereas when applying the advanced finite element method, all the first three natural frequencies of the simply supported and clamped-free beams as well as the first two natural frequencies of the clamped-clamped beam can be obtained. In this table the blank units indicate the results which cannot be derived using that specific number of elements for the corresponding boundary condition and the method used.

It can also be concluded from Table 1 that advanced finite element method is not as sensitive as conventional finite element method to the number of elements used to derive the natural frequencies. Even with low number of elements acceptable accuracy can be obtained using advanced finite element method.

II. Thickness-tapered width-tapered beams with constant-thickness-tapering-angle and varying width-ratio: In this case the thickness-tapering angle is held constant at 0.57 degrees and the width-ratio ($\frac{b_2}{b_1}$) varies from 0.2 to 0.8. The effect of width-ratio on the natural frequencies of the thickness-tapered beams is studied and is shown in Figure 4. Three boundary conditions (simply supported, clamped-free and clamped-clamped) and four thickness-tapering configurations (configurations A, B, C and D) are considered for this case. The results are compared with that obtained using conventional finite element method [20] and are shown in Table 2. Excellent accuracy has been observed.

It is shown in Figure 4 that due to the boundary condition constraint, clamped-clamped beams have the highest natural frequencies and clamped-free beams have the lowest natural frequencies.

It can be concluded based on the results shown in Table 2 that configuration D has the highest natural frequencies and is the most stiff configuration, configuration C and configuration B have the second highest and the third highest natural frequencies respectively. Configuration A has the lowest natural

frequencies and is the least stiff configuration among all the considered configurations.

It can be observed from Figure 4 that as the width-ratio of the thickness-tapered width-tapered simply supported and clamped-clamped beams increases their natural frequencies will increase, the natural frequencies of thickness-tapered width-tapered clamped-free beams on the other hand, will decrease which is due to weight increase at the free end of the clamped-free beams.

III. Thickness-tapered width-tapered beams with constant width-ratio and varying thickness-tapering angle: In this comparison the width-ratio is held constant ($\frac{b_2}{b_1} = 0.5$) and the thickness-tapering angle varies. Thickness-tapering angle of a beam increases as its length decreases. In this case the effect of thickness-tapering angle on the response of width-tapered beams is studied and is shown in Figure 5. Three boundary conditions (simply supported, clamped-free and clamped-clamped) and four thickness-tapering configurations (configurations A, B, C and D) are considered for this case. The results are compared with that obtained using conventional finite element method [20] and are shown in Table 3. Excellent accuracy has been observed.

It is expected that as the length of a beam decreases (thickness-tapering angle increases) the natural frequencies of the beam will increase, and it is shown in Figure 5 and Table 3 that the model used in this study successfully captures this trend.

3.3 Mode shapes

First, second and third mode shapes of a thickness-tapered beam (configuration D) with 36 to 12 plies taper and that of a uniform beam with 36 plies with three boundary conditions (simply supported, clamped-free and clamped-clamped) are determined and shown in Figure 6. It can be seen from the mode shapes that the maximum deflections are shifted to the thin end of the tapered beams. It can be concluded from the mode shapes that tapering the beam will alter its mode shapes.

4 Conclusion

In this study, the advanced finite element formulation has been developed for the free vibration analysis of variable-thickness variable-width laminated composite beams based on classical laminate theory. In the case of uniform laminated composite beams, natural frequencies obtained using advanced finite element method have been

compared with the exact natural frequencies and with those obtained using conventional finite element method. It has been indicated that use of advanced finite element method for the free vibration analysis of the beams results in better accuracy of the obtained natural frequencies compared to those obtained using conventional finite element method, especially when using less number of elements in the analysis. Consequently accuracy can be obtained more efficiently and rapidly by increasing the number of degrees of freedom in the element rather than increasing the number of elements.

Based on the results obtained, it is concluded that configuration D has the highest values of natural frequencies, and then configurations C and B respectively have the second highest and the third highest natural frequencies. The configuration A has the lowest natural frequencies among all configurations. Consequently configuration D is the stiffest configuration. The size and the location of resin pockets and how they are separated have a large effect on the stiffness of the beams. In configuration D, large resin pockets are separated by a bent continuous composite ply which increases the stiffness of this configuration whereas in the other configurations composite plies are dropped somehow that there does not exist any continuous ply between the resin pockets.

It can be illustrated that as the width-ratio of the beam increases, the natural frequencies of the simply supported and the clamped-clamped beams will increase while the natural frequencies of the clamped-free beams will decrease.

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Fig 1. Different configurations of the thickness-taper of the composite beam (longitudinal view of the beam)

Fig 2. Width-taper of the composite beam (top view of the beam)

Fig 3. Arbitrary ply in the thickness-tapered composite beam

Fig 4. Fundamental natural frequencies of beams with constant thickness-tapering angle (0.57 degrees) and varying width-ratio for simply supported, clamped-free and clamped-clamped boundary conditions

Fig 5. Fundamental natural frequencies of beams with constant width-ratio ($b_2/b_1 = 0.5$) and varying thickness-tapering angle for simply supported, clamped-free and clamped-clamped boundary conditions

Fig 6. First, second and third mode shapes of uniform and thickness-tapered uniform-width simply supported, clamped-free and clamped-clamped beams

Table 1: Comparison of exact and finite element natural frequencies for simply supported, clamped-free and clamped-clamped uniform beams

The Lowest Three Natural Frequencies ($\times 10^3$ rad/s) for Simply Supported Uniform Beam								
Mode	Exact NF			1 E	2 E	3 E	4 E	10 E
1 st	1.3667	CFEM	Natural Frequency	1.5169	1.3721	1.3678	1.367	1.3667
			Percentage Error	10.99	0.39	0.08	0.03	0
		AFEM	Natural Frequency	1.3667	1.3667	1.3667	1.3667	1.3667
			Percentage Error	0	0	0	0	0
2 nd	5.4667	CFEM	Natural Frequency	6.9514	6.0676	5.5314	5.4883	5.4673
			Percentage Error	27.16	10.99	1.18	0.39	0.01
		AFEM	Natural Frequency	5.4669	5.4668	5.4667	5.4667	5.4667
			Percentage Error	0	0	0	0	0
3 rd	12.3002	CFEM	Natural Frequency	-	15.2515	13.6522	12.5249	12.3068
			Percentage Error	-	23.99	10.99	1.83	0.05
		AFEM	Natural Frequency	12.6444	12.3004	12.3002	12.3002	12.3002
			Percentage Error	2.8	0	0	0	0
The Lowest Three Natural Frequencies ($\times 10^3$ rad/s) for Clamped-Free Uniform Beam								
Mode	Exact NF			1 E	2 E	3 E	4 E	10 E
1 st	0.4869	CFEM	Natural Frequency	0.4892	0.4871	0.4869	0.4869	0.4869
			Percentage Error	0.48	0.05	0.01	0	0
		AFEM	Natural Frequency	0.4869	0.4869	0.4869	0.4869	0.4869
			Percentage Error	0	0	0	0	0
2 nd	3.0511	CFEM	Natural Frequency	4.8199	3.0771	3.0612	3.0548	3.0513
			Percentage Error	57.97	0.85	0.33	0.12	0.01
		AFEM	Natural Frequency	3.0513	3.0512	3.0512	3.0512	3.0512
			Percentage Error	0.01	0	0	0	0
3 rd	8.544	CFEM	Natural Frequency	-	10.4073	8.6499	8.6096	8.5457
			Percentage Error	-	21.81	1.24	0.77	0.02
		AFEM	Natural Frequency	8.5532	8.5435	8.5435	8.5435	8.5435
			Percentage Error	0.11	-0.01	-0.01	-0.01	-0.01
The Lowest Three Natural Frequencies ($\times 10^3$ rad/s) for Clamped-Clamped Uniform Beam								
Mode	Exact NF			1 E	2 E	3 E	4 E	10 E
1 st	3.0981	CFEM	Natural Frequency	-	3.1483	3.1108	3.1022	3.0982
			Percentage Error	-	1.62	0.41	0.13	0
		AFEM	Natural Frequency	3.0982	3.0981	3.0981	3.0981	3.0981
			Percentage Error	0	0	0	0	0
2 nd	8.5397	CFEM	Natural Frequency	-	11.3515	8.7106	8.6191	8.5423
			Percentage Error	-	32.93	2	0.93	0.03
		AFEM	Natural Frequency	8.5429	8.5401	8.5401	8.5401	8.5401
			Percentage Error	0.04	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
3 rd	16.7432	CFEM	Natural Frequency	-	-	20.2594	17.0996	16.7585
			Percentage Error	-	-	21	2.13	0.09
		AFEM	Natural Frequency	17.6737	16.7447	16.742	16.742	16.742
			Percentage Error	5.56	0.01	-0.01	-0.01	-0.01

Table 2. Comparison of the natural frequencies obtained using advanced and conventional finite element methods for laminated composite beams with constant thickness-tapering angle and varying width ratio

NF (rad/s)	Simply Supported											
	Configuration A			Configuration B			Configuration C			Configuration D		
width-ratio	0.2	0.4	0.8	0.2	0.4	0.8	0.2	0.4	0.8	0.2	0.4	0.8
ω_1 (AFEM)	2246	2332	2411	2133	2222	2306	2172	2264	2351	2535	2625	2707
ω_1 (CFEM)	2253	2337	2413	2145	2232	2318	2184	2272	2355	2550	2649	2721
% differ	0.35	0.22	0.1	0.54	0.42	0.53	0.55	0.34	0.18	0.57	0.9	0.53
ω_2 (AFEM)	10027	9976	9912	9826	9769	9698	10028	9968	9894	11104	11072	11019
ω_2 (CFEM)	10068	10005	9932	9876	9808	9728	10074	9998	9915	11158	11112	11050
% differ	0.41	0.29	0.2	0.51	0.4	0.3	0.45	0.3	0.21	0.49	0.36	0.28
ω_3 (AFEM)	22342	22252	22155	21894	21799	21695	22334	22233	22125	24502	24409	24303
ω_3 (CFEM)	22438	22319	22202	22010	21887	21762	22436	22303	22172	24608	24483	24360
% differ	0.43	0.3	0.21	0.52	0.4	0.31	0.46	0.31	0.22	0.43	0.3	0.24
NF (rad/s)	Clamped-Clamped											
	Configuration A			Configuration B			Configuration C			Configuration D		
width-ratio	0.2	0.4	0.8	0.2	0.4	0.8	0.2	0.4	0.8	0.2	0.4	0.8
ω_1 (AFEM)	5604	5633	5581	5534	5550	5485	5665	5679	5610	5908	5964	5942
ω_1 (CFEM)	5563	5604	5555	5492	5520	5467	5630	5653	5586	5870	5927	5909
% differ	0.73	0.52	0.48	0.77	0.53	0.33	0.62	0.47	0.43	0.65	0.62	0.56
ω_2 (AFEM)	15403	15435	15359	15113	15131	15040	15458	15473	15375	16778	16854	16818
ω_2 (CFEM)	15301	15359	15288	15025	15058	14979	15368	15404	15312	16681	16783	16745
% differ	0.67	0.5	0.46	0.58	0.48	0.41	0.59	0.44	0.41	0.58	0.43	0.43
ω_3 (AFEM)	30148	30171	30081	29512	29524	29421	30167	30173	30063	32765	32833	32780
ω_3 (CFEM)	29963	30029	29949	29354	29401	29306	30004	30049	29946	32553	32667	32621
% differ	0.62	0.47	0.44	0.54	0.42	0.39	0.54	0.41	0.39	0.65	0.51	0.49
NF (rad/s)	Clamped-Free											
	Configuration A			Configuration B			Configuration C			Configuration D		
width-ratio	0.2	0.4	0.8	0.2	0.4	0.8	0.2	0.4	0.8	0.2	0.4	0.8
ω_1 (AFEM)	2135	1837	1534	2233	1928	1617	2301	1986	1667	2211	1910	1595
ω_1 (CFEM)	2149	1842	1547	2284	1865	1649	2322	1996	1672	2253	1898	1555
% differ	0.64	0.32	0.84	2.23	3.33	1.91	0.92	0.49	0.3	1.85	0.63	2.6
ω_2 (AFEM)	7515	7049	6621	7508	7040	6609	7695	7216	6775	8158	7639	7169
ω_2 (CFEM)	7601	7105	6657	7603	7100	6646	7787	7277	6814	8245	7713	7207
% differ	1.13	0.79	0.54	1.25	0.85	0.57	1.18	0.83	0.57	1.06	0.95	0.53
ω_3 (AFEM)	17383	16882	16445	17150	16645	16201	17540	17024	16570	19161	18607	18138
ω_3 (CFEM)	17610	17028	16539	17379	16801	16302	17778	17179	16672	19408	18778	18244
% differ	1.29	0.86	0.57	1.32	0.93	0.62	1.34	0.9	0.61	1.27	0.91	0.58

Table 3. Comparison of the natural frequencies obtained using advanced and conventional finite element methods for laminated composite beams with varying thickness-tapering angle and constant width-ratio

NF (rad/s)	Simply Supported											
	Configuration A			Configuration B			Configuration C			Configuration D		
Angle (deg)	0.344	0.43	0.573	0.344	0.43	0.573	0.344	0.43	0.573	0.344	0.43	0.573
L (m)	0.25	0.2	0.15	0.25	0.2	0.15	0.25	0.2	0.15	0.25	0.2	0.15
$\frac{L}{H_L}$	56	44	33	56	44	33	56	44	33	56	44	33
$\frac{L}{b_l}$	17	13	10	17	13	10	17	13	10	17	13	10
ω_1 (AFEM)	758	1184	2104	810	1266	2251	826	1290	2293	955	1493	2653
ω_1 (CFEM)	760	1188	2110	816	1270	2260	827	1296	2299	959	1502	2654
% differ	0.36	0.34	0.27	0.71	0.34	0.42	0.21	0.47	0.26	0.41	0.65	0.03
ω_2 (AFEM)	3211	5017	8920	3509	5482	9746	3580	5594	9944	3980	6219	11056
ω_2 (CFEM)	3221	5033	8949	3520	5500	9771	3590	5609	9971	3992	6240	11093
% differ	0.32	0.3	0.32	0.33	0.32	0.25	0.27	0.28	0.27	0.29	0.34	0.33
ω_3 (AFEM)	7156	11180	19876	7835	12243	21764	7991	12486	22197	8775	13711	24374
ω_3 (CFEM)	7179	11217	19940	7863	12284	21839	8013	12521	22259	8800	13750	24446
% differ	0.32	0.32	0.32	0.35	0.33	0.34	0.27	0.28	0.28	0.28	0.28	0.29
NF (rad/s)	Clamped-Clamped											
	Configuration A			Configuration B			Configuration C			Configuration D		
ω_1 (AFEM)	1820	2843	5054	1994	3116	5539	2040	3188	5667	2148	3357	5967
ω_1 (CFEM)	1808	2826	5024	1984	3105	5511	2031	3174	5642	2137	3343	5940
% differ	0.62	0.61	0.6	0.49	0.34	0.5	0.44	0.43	0.45	0.51	0.4	0.46
ω_2 (AFEM)	4977	7776	13824	5441	8502	15114	5564	8693	15454	6069	9482	16856
ω_2 (CFEM)	4947	7730	13742	5418	8467	15053	5540	8657	15389	6044	9443	16790
% differ	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.44	0.42	0.41	0.42	0.42	0.42	0.4	0.41	0.39
ω_3 (AFEM)	9720	15187	26998	10622	16596	29503	10855	16960	30151	11819	18467	32829
ω_3 (CFEM)	9665	15101	26847	10581	16531	29389	10812	16893	30031	11761	18376	32671
% differ	0.57	0.57	0.56	0.39	0.39	0.39	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.5	0.5	0.48
NF (rad/s)	Clamped-Free											
	Configuration A			Configuration B			Configuration C			Configuration D		
ω_1 (AFEM)	581	908	1614	657	1027	1826	677	1058	1882	651	1017	1808
ω_1 (CFEM)	583	913	1617	677	1053	1856	681	1070	1891	674	998	1780
% differ	0.31	0.59	0.19	2.96	2.46	1.65	0.5	1.07	0.48	3.41	1.88	1.55
ω_2 (AFEM)	2258	3527	6271	2483	3880	6897	2545	3977	7070	2694	4209	7482
ω_2 (CFEM)	2274	3554	6317	2506	3906	6952	2564	4007	7123	2713	4235	7527
% differ	0.74	0.73	0.73	0.92	0.68	0.78	0.74	0.75	0.75	0.71	0.61	0.6
ω_3 (AFEM)	5419	8467	15052	5939	9280	16497	6074	9491	16873	6642	10378	18448
ω_3 (CFEM)	5463	8536	15176	5987	9352	16633	6123	9567	17008	6692	10455	18591
% differ	0.81	0.81	0.82	0.81	0.77	0.82	0.79	0.79	0.8	0.75	0.74	0.77